

International Conference

"Social, Tech, and Natural Sciences in the Multidisciplinary Advent"

Hybrid – online & in-person

August 15, 2024, Cambridge, UNITED KINGDOM

Registration of the participants	08.00-08.30
Event welcome	08.30-08.45
Plenary speakers	08.45-11.00
<i>BRINDUSA STERPU, Centre for Mountain Economy & CBM International University</i>	08.45-09.15
<i>Exploring the Frontiers of Natural Sciences in the Multidisciplinary Advent: Bridging Biology, Physics, and Environmental Science for a Holistic Understanding of Earth's Complex Systems</i>	09.15-10.45
<i>MIHAI COVACI, Hyperion University & CBM International University</i>	
<i>Integrating Social Dynamics and Technological Innovation in the Multidisciplinary Advent: Navigating the Intersections of Human Behavior, Digital Transformation, and Societal Impact</i>	
Q & A	10.45-11.00
Parallel sessions	11.00-12.00
<i>Session 1 – Natural Sciences in the Multidisciplinary Era</i>	
<i>EVA CLARK, Akademos Learning UK</i>	11.00-11.30
<i>Natural Sciences in the Multidisciplinary Era: Integrating Knowledge Across Disciplines to Address Complex Global Challenges</i>	11.30-12.00
<i>ALBERT LEWIS, 9462-9755 Quebec Canada</i>	
<i>Natural Sciences in the Multidisciplinary Era: Bridging Disciplines to</i>	

<i>Tackle Complex Global Challenges through Collaborative Innovation and Knowledge Integration</i>	
<p><i>Session 2 – Social and Tech in the Multidisciplinary Era</i></p> <p><i>JACK BAILEY, Centre for Risk Studies in Economic and Social Sciences Austria</i></p> <p><i>Social and Technology Integration in the Multidisciplinary Era: Exploring Synergies for Innovation, Social Impact, and Global Development</i></p>	11.00-11.30
<p><i>OLIVIA CAMPBELL, Zealandina Agency UK</i></p> <p><i>Social and Technology Integration in the Multidisciplinary Era: Uniting Disciplines to Drive Innovation, Address Social Challenges, and Foster Sustainable Global Development</i></p>	11.30-12.00
Coffee break	12.00-12.15
<p><i>Session 1 – Natural Sciences in the Multidisciplinary Era</i></p> <p><i>CARLA SELMA, Akademos Agency UK</i></p> <p><i>Natural Sciences in the Multidisciplinary Era: Bridging Disciplines for Global Solutions</i></p>	12.15-12.45
<p><i>PARVATI AARAV, CBM International University</i></p> <p><i>Natural Sciences in the Multidisciplinary Era: Fostering Cross-Disciplinary Collaboration to Develop Innovative Solutions for Global Sustainability Challenges</i></p>	12.45-13.15
<p><i>Session 2 – Social and Tech in the Multidisciplinary Era</i></p> <p><i>LASHMI DURGA, CBM International University</i></p> <p><i>Social and Technology Integration in the Multidisciplinary Era: Leveraging Cross-Disciplinary Collaboration to Drive Innovation, Solve Social Challenges, and Promote Sustainable Global Development</i></p>	12.15-12.45
<p><i>SHI CHEN, CBM International University</i></p> <p><i>Social and Technology Integration in the Multidisciplinary Era: Exploring Cross-Disciplinary Approaches to Innovate Solutions,</i></p>	12.45-13.15

CBM International University USA

Akados Learning UK

9462-9755 Quebec CA & AT (Centre for Risk Studies in Economic and Social Sciences)

<i>Tackle Global Challenges, and Promote Sustainable Societal Progress</i>	
Q&A	13.15-13.45
Concluding remarks	13.45-14.00

Location: Wellington House, East Road, Cambridge, CB1 1BH, United Kingdom